

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

USE OF SYNTHETIC PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS IN AGRICULTURE AND BIOTECHNOLOGY

**Tsygankova V.,
Voloshchuk L.,
Andrusevich Ya.,
Kopich V.,**

Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

Oliynyk O.,

Department of Ecobiotechnology and Biodiversity, Faculty of plant protection, biotechnology and ecology, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

Stefanovska T.,

Department of Entomology, Integrated Pest Management and Plant Quarantine, the National University of Life and Environmental Sciences, Kyiv, Ukraine

Pidlisnyuk V.,

Department of the Environmental Chemistry and Technology, Jan Evangelista Purkyně University, Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic

Pilyo S.,

Klyuchko S.,

Brovarets V.

Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

Abstract

An urgent task of modern agriculture and biotechnology is the development of new environmentally friendly plant growth regulators to increase the growth and yield of plants and protect them from abiotic and biotic stress factors. Synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur based on pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives are the most promising environmentally friendly biologically active compounds. Our laboratory, field and *in vitro* studies have proven their high efficiency in growing important agricultural, industrial, and floricultural crops. These synthetic plant growth regulators exhibit high growth-regulating activity when used at low non-toxic to human and animal health concentrations ranging from 10^{-5} M to 10^{-8} M. The practical use of synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur for intensifying the growth and development of agricultural, industrial, and floricultural crops, increasing their productivity, and improving crop adaptation to stress factors is proposed.

Keywords: plant growth regulators, pyridine, pyrimidine, Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur, plant growth and productivity, agriculture, biotechnology.

Today, there is a great demand for new effective plant growth regulators, which is evidenced by the volume of their sales in the world, which is approximately 1.2 billion dollars USA per year [1]. Currently, synthetic derivatives of pyridine and pyrimidine are the most promising for use as effective and environmentally friendly plant growth regulators, herbicides and fungicides [2, 3]. This review article describes the results of our previously published works [4, 5, 6], in which the effect of synthetic plant growth regulators: Ivin (N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine), Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) on plant growth in field, laboratory and *in vitro* conditions, crop productivity and adaptation to stress factors was studied. Synthetic plant growth regulators have been developed in the Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of

Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.

Global climate change and environmental pollution are negatively impacting growth and reducing yields of one of the world's most important widely grown crops, sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) [7, 8]. The effect of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur on growth and productivity of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Bastion under field conditions was studied in the work [4]. The growth-regulating activity of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur was compared with the growth-regulating activity of the auxin IAA (1*H*-Indol-3-yl)acetic acid). It was found that the treatment of seeds before planting in the soil with water solutions of Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur, used at a concentration of 10^{-7} M, contributes to an increase in morphological parameters (length of shoot and root, fresh weight of plant and

basket) of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Bastion grown in field conditions for 3 months.

The results of the effect of Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur on morphological parameters of sunflower plants are illustrated in Figure 1. The average length of shoot increased: by 8,2603 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Ivin, by 6,383 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Methyur, by 8,1352 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 1, A). The average length of root increased: by 3,2231 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Ivin, by 20,5638 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Methyur, by 9,259 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 1, B). The average fresh weight of plant increased: by 124,1379 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Ivin, by 89,6552 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Methyur, by 97,0443 % - in plants obtained from seeds

treated with Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 1, C). The average fresh weight of basket increased: by 90,678 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Ivin, by 83,8983 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Methyur, by 72,8814 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 1, D).

The growth-regulating activity of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur was higher than the growth-regulating activity of the auxin IAA used at the same concentration of 10^{-7} M. The average length of shoot increased by 0,8761 %, the average length of root increased by 1,33 %, the average fresh weight of plant increased by 46,3054 %, the average fresh weight of baskets by 61,0169 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with IAA, compared to the control (Figure 1, A, B, C, D).

Figure 1. The morphological parameters of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Bastion grown for 3 month in field conditions: A - the average length of shoot (%), B - the average length of root (%), C - the average fresh weight of plant (%), D - the average fresh weight of basket (%).

The obtained results suggested that the high growth-regulating activity of Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur is explained by their specific auxin-like stimulating effect on the proliferation, elongation and differentiation of plant cells, which are the main processes of the formation and development of plant shoots and roots, as well on the biosynthesis, metabolism and signaling of endogenous auxins in plant cells [9].

It was found that the treatment of seeds before planting in the soil with water solutions of Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur, used at a concentration of 10^{-7} M, contributes also to an increase in biochemical parameters (content of chlorophylls a and b, and carotenoids) [10] of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) variety Bastion grown in field conditions for 3 months.

The results of the effect of Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur on biochemical parameters parameters of sunflower plants are illustrated in Figure 2. The content of chlorophyll a increased by 11,1659 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 2). The content of chlorophyll b increased: by 47,7819 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Ivin, by 62,1236 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Methyur, by 60,5887 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 2). The content of chlorophylls a+b increased: by 11,8394 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Ivin, by 16,468 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with Methyur, by 25,841 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with

Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 2). A comparative analysis showed also that the biochemical parameters (content of chlorophylls and carotenoids) in the leaves of experimental sunflower plants exceeded those of plants obtained from seeds treated with IAA, the content of chlorophyll b increased by 28,2853 %, the content of chlorophylls a+b increased by 4,7939 % - in plants obtained from seeds treated with IAA, compared to the control (Figure 2).

A decrease in content of chlorophyll a was observed in plants obtained from seeds treated with IAA, Ivin and Methyur, and decrease in content of carotenoids was observed in plants obtained from seeds treated with IAA, Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur, compared to the control (Figure 2). It has been suggested that the decrease in the concentration of chlorophyll a and carotenoids is associated with a significant increase in the fresh weight of the plant.

Figure 2.

The biochemical parameters of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) variety Bastion grown for 3 month in field conditions: Cchl (a+b) – concentration of chlorophylls a and b (µg/ml), Cchl a – concentration of chlorophyll a (µg/ml), Cchl b – concentration of chlorophyll b (µg/ml), Ccar – concentration of carotenoids (µg/ml).

The obtained results confirmed the possibility of using plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur or Kamethur in a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ for the pre-sowing treatment of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) seeds variety Bastion to increase the length of shoot and root in the vegetative phase, as well as to increase the main indicators of plant productivity - the fresh weight of the plant and basket, and the content of photosynthetic pigments, in particular, chlorophylls b and a+b in plant leaves.

Soil contamination with trace elements (TEs) is a pressing problem limiting the cultivation of agricultural crops; however, the non-food energy crop *Miscanthus × giganteus* (*M×g*) showing a high biomass yield and immense lignocellulose content can be grown on such soil. The effect of synthetic plant growth regulator Kamethur and polycomponent biostimulant Charkor (based on the complex of synthetic plant growth regulator Ivin with synthetic auxin NAA (1-naphthylacetic acid) and natural biostimulant Emistim C containing secondary metabolites of the root endophyte fungus *Panax Ginsed M.* (i.e. a mixture of amino acids, carbohydrates, fatty acids, polysaccharides, phytohormones,

and microelements) was studied when *M×g* was cultivated in TE-contaminated soils from Vseborice (former mining) and Chomutov (former military), in the Northern Czech Republic [5].

The results obtained showed that Kamethur contributed to an increase in the biomass of leaves and stems (by 57,1% and 125%, respectively), while Charkor only increased the biomass of leaves (by 49,5%) when *M×g* was cultivated in the more polluted soil of Vseborice (Figure 3).

Analysis of the comprehensive bio-concentration index (a predictable indicator to access the ability of phytoagent to accumulate multiple TEs) it was revealed that Charkor increased the accumulation of elements essential for plant development (EEs) in leaves and decreased in stems the potentially toxic (PTEs) elements, by 33,3% and 11,4%, respectively, while Kamethur decreased stem accumulation of EEs by 11,4% and increased the accumulation of PTEs by 23,3%, when *M×g* was cultivated in the more contaminated soil from Vseborice.

Figure 3. Leaves and stem's DW of *M×g* grown in the Chomutov and Vseborice soils. Different letters indicate a significant difference between the values ($p < 0.001$).

Statistical evaluation of the current results and literature data illustrated the ability of Charkor to reduce the uptake of PTEs, which is critical for converting clean biomass to bioproducts. It can be recommended for the reduction of PTEs uptake to biomass when the crop is cultivated in varied contaminated soils. Kamethur can be recommended to increase the biomass of leaves and stems when cultivating *M×g* on various polluted soils. Further research should confirm the influence of Kamethur and Charkor on the bioparameters and phytoremediation processes of *M×g* at the field plantation level.

Rose, belonging to the genus *Rosa* L. of the Rosaceae family, is a floricultural crop widely used in the horticulture, perfumery, pharmaceutical and food industries [11]. In our work [6], we studied the effect of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur on increasing the efficiency of miniature rose (*Rosa mini* L.) organogenesis *in vitro*. The growth regulatory activity of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Ka-

methur was compared with the activity of plant hormone auxin IAA. It was shown that the effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur used at concentrations of 10^{-5} M, 10^{-6} M, 10^{-7} M per 1 liter of MS (Murashige and Skoog) medium on the organogenesis of shoots and roots of miniature rose (*Rosa mini* L.) *in vitro* is similar or higher than the effect of the plant hormone auxin IAA used at the same concentrations. The synthetic plant growth regulators showed the highest effect on the organogenesis of shoots and roots of miniature rose (*Rosa mini* L.) *in vitro* when used in concentrations: Ivin at concentrations of 10^{-5} M and 10^{-6} M, Kamethur at concentrations of 10^{-5} M and 10^{-6} M, Methyur at concentrations of 10^{-5} M and 10^{-7} M (Figure 4, A and B). The plant hormone auxin IAA showed the highest effect on the organogenesis of shoots and roots of miniature rose (*Rosa mini* L.) *in vitro* when used as component of the MS medium at concentrations of 10^{-6} M and 10^{-7} M (Figure 4, A and B).

A

B

Figure 4. Organogenesis of shoots and roots of miniature rose (*Rosa mini L.*) in vitro, measured on the 28th day of cultivation, (A): 1- control hormone-free MS medium, 2 - MS medium containing Ivin at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$, 3 - MS medium containing Kamethur at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$, 4 - MS medium containing Methyur at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$, 5 - MS medium containing plant hormone auxin IAA at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$; (B): 1- control hormone-free MS medium, 2 - MS medium containing Ivin at a concentration of $10^{-7}M$, 3 - MS medium containing Kamethur at a concentration of $10^{-7}M$, 4 - MS medium containing Methyur at a concentration of $10^{-7}M$, 5 - MS medium containing plant hormone auxin IAA at a concentration of $10^{-7}M$

According to the parameters of length of shoots (cm) per explant, measured on the 21st and 28th days of cultivation, synthetic plant growth regulators showed the highest activity: Ivin at concentration of $10^{-6}M$ ($1,75 \pm 0,12$ cm and $2,82 \pm 0,19$ cm), Kamethur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($2,1 \pm 0,37$ cm and $2,75 \pm 0,28$ cm) and $10^{-6}M$ ($1,8 \pm 0,24$ cm and $2,87 \pm 0,17$ cm), and Methyur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($2,8 \pm 0,24$ cm and $2,75 \pm 0,63$ cm) and $10^{-7}M$ ($3,42 \pm 0,95$ cm and $3,92 \pm 0,64$ cm), respectively, compared with lower parameters of length of shoots (cm) per explant obtained on the control hormone-free medium MS ($1,0 \pm 0,57$ cm and $2,17 \pm 0,33$ cm). According to the parameters of length of roots (cm) per explant, measured on the 21st and 28th days of cultivation, synthetic plant growth regulator showed the highest activity: Kamethur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($2,75 \pm 0,28$ cm and $2,83 \pm 0,33$ cm), $10^{-6}M$ ($2,08 \pm 0,39$ cm and $3,15 \pm 0,33$ cm) and $10^{-7}M$ ($1,55 \pm 0,44$ cm and $2,83 \pm 0,21$ cm), respectively, compared with lower parameters of length of roots (cm) per explant obtained on the control hormone-free medium MS ($1,17 \pm 0,7$ cm and $2,0 \pm 0,57$ cm). According to the parameters of number of roots (pcs) per explant, measured on the 21st and 28th days of cultivation, synthetic plant growth regulators showed the highest activity: Ivin at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($6,0 \pm 1,39$ pcs and $6,33 \pm 1,30$ pcs) and $10^{-6}M$ ($6,16 \pm 1,37$ pcs and $6,33 \pm 1,3$

pcs), Kamethur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($5,8 \pm 1,13$ pcs and $6,6 \pm 1,47$ pcs), $10^{-6}M$ ($6,33 \pm 1,19$ pcs and $7,83 \pm 2,11$ pcs) and $10^{-7}M$ ($5,88 \pm 1,28$ pcs and $6,19 \pm 1,32$ pcs), Methyur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($7,5 \pm 1,49$ pcs and $7,92 \pm 2,73$ pcs) and $10^{-6}M$ ($5,95 \pm 1,25$ pcs and $6,65 \pm 1,5$ pcs), respectively, compared with lower parameters of number of roots (pcs) per explant obtained on the control hormone-free medium MS ($3,0 \pm 1,39$ pcs and $3,5 \pm 1,27$ pcs). According to the parameters of the frequency (%) of shoot rooting, measured on the 21st and 28th days of cultivation, synthetic plant growth regulators showed the highest activity: Ivin at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($67,75 \pm 0,93$ % and $67,8 \pm 4,18$ %) and $10^{-6}M$ ($80,17 \pm 2,74$ % and $80,83 \pm 3,05$ %), Kamethur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($67,2 \pm 4,12$ % and $73,75 \pm 3,69$ %), $10^{-6}M$ ($73,67 \pm 2,51$ % and $99,83 \pm 0,33$ %) and $10^{-7}M$ ($60,67 \pm 2,61$ % and $67,17 \pm 1,85$ %), Methyur at concentrations of $10^{-5}M$ ($87,75 \pm 3,24$ % and $87,33 \pm 5,10$ %) and $10^{-7}M$ ($80,33 \pm 2,51$ % and $87,5 \pm 1,41$ %), respectively, compared with lower parameters of the frequency (%) of shoot rooting obtained on the control hormone-free medium MS ($39,33 \pm 7,99$ % and $53,17 \pm 4,84$ %).

The plant hormone auxin IAA showed the highest activity in relation to the parameters of shoot and root organogenesis, measured on the 21st and 28th days of cultivation, according to the length of shoots (cm) per

explant at concentrations of 10^{-7} M ($2,85 \pm 0,77$ cm and $2,93 \pm 0,32$ cm) and for the frequency (%) of shoot rooting at concentrations of 10^{-6} M ($60,33 \pm 1,4$ % and $80,16 \pm 2,74$ %) and 10^{-7} M ($93,17 \pm 1,55$ % and $93,17 \pm 1,55$ %), respectively.

The obtained results showed both cytokinin- and auxin-like effects of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur on the processes of elongation, division and differentiation of the isolated plant cells, which are the main processes of organogenesis of shoot and root meristems of miniature rose (*Rosa mini* L.) *in vitro*. The application of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur for micropropagation of the miniature rose (*Rosa mini* L.) through *in vitro* culture is proposed.

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